

MNDO Method of Studies of Isomers of C₆H₆

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The MNDO method has been applied to compute the heat of formation of thirty isomers of C₆H₆. A comparison of these values indicates the variation in their relative stabilities. These variations have been correlated with the structural features of the isomers. The results of MNDO calculation were compared with the *ab initio* Hartree-Fock Roothan/6-31G* calculation and the experimental data for the isomer Dewar benzene.

The literature of the last few years contains reports on the structures and stabilities of some isomers of C₆H₆. However, no systematic study seems to have been made on all the possible isomeric structures and their relative stabilities. Therefore, we report here a discussion on the relative stabilities of C₆H₆ isomers based on their heat of formation evaluated by the MNDO method¹.

Results and Discussion

The heats of formation (ΔH_f) of the thirty isomers of C₆H₆ (Fig. 1) have been evaluated (Table 1). Each isomer of C₆H₆ (having 12 atoms and hence 30 geometrical parameters) was fully optimised. As expected, benzene (1), the most stable isomer, has the lowest heat of formation. At the other extreme, structure 30 has the highest ΔH_f value; obviously this structure is associated with the least stability among the isomers considered in this study. The other isomers (2–29) have intermediate values of ΔH_f . It is interesting to note that the acyclic isomers (3–6) have almost the same heats of formation. In addition, their ΔH_f values are considerably lesser than those for the cyclic isomers. Therefore, the existence of these acyclic isomers is not an impossibility, though they are likely to be less stable than benzene.

Among the isomers of (CH)₆, Dewar benzene (7), benzvalene (10) and prismane (17) have energies between those of benzene and 3,3'-bicyclopropenyl structure (23). Therefore, the intermediate cyclic structures, 7 through 22, should be more stable than the bicyclopropenyl molecules.

As a sample, the results of the MNDO calculation were compared with the *ab initio* Hartree-Fock Roothan/6-31G* calculation and the experimental data

Fig. 1. Structures of C₆H₆ isomers.

TABLE 1—HEATS OF FORMATION OF C₆H₆ ISOMERS CALCULATED BY MNDO METHOD

Structure no.	Molecule	ΔH_f kcal mol ⁻¹
1	Benzene	21.2
2	Fulvene	53.6
3	Hex-2,4-diyne	68.9
4	Hex-3-yne-1,5-diene	72.3
5	Hex-2,3,4,5-tetraene	85.9
6	Hex-1,2,4,5-tetraene	87.8
7	Dewar benzene	89.7
8	1,2,3-Trimethylenecyclopropane	90.5
9	Cyclohex-1,2,4-triene	95.6
10	Benzvalene	101.6
11	Spirohex-2,5-diene	110.0
12	Bicyclo[1.1.0]butyl-3-ethyne	113.8
13	Cyclohex-1-yne-4-ene	115.8
14	4-Cyclopropylmethylenecyclopropene	116.4
15	Bicyclo[1.1.0]butyl-2-ethyne	118.2
16	4-Methylenespiropent-2-ene	118.4
17	Prismane	121.9
18	3-Methylenetricyclo[2.1.1.0 ^{0,2,5}]pentane	124.9
19	Bicyclo[2.1.0]hex-1,2-diene	126.0
20	1,1'-Bicyclopropenyl	126.8
21	1,3'-Bicyclopropenyl	134.2
22	2-Methylspiropent-2,4-diene	134.9
23	3,3'-Bicyclopropenyl	141.0
24	Cyclopropenyl-2-bicyclo[1.1.0]butane	144.6
25	Bicyclo[2.2.0]hex-1(4),2-diene	145.6
26	Vinyltetrahedrane	148.0
27	Tricyclo[2.1.1.0 ^{1,4}]hex-2-ene	172.2
28	3-Methylenebicyclo[2.1.0]pent-1(4)-ene	174.7
29	Tricyclo[2.1.1.0 ^{1,5} 0 ^{2,4}]hex-1(4)-ene	199.5
30	2-Methylbicyclo[2.1.0]pent-1(4),2-diene	202.3

for the isomer Dewar benzene. The structure of Dewar benzene is shown in Fig. 2. The optimised (MNDO and 6-31G^{*}) and experimental (gas-phase electron diffraction and microwave) structural parameters of Dewar benzene have been compared (Table 2). Liu *et al.*² performed *ab initio* calculations using the restricted Hartree-Fock (RHF) self-consistent-field (SCF) theory in conjunction with the 6-31G^{*} basis set. The gas-phase electron diffraction study of Dewar benzene has been reported by McNeill and Scholer³ and the microwave result obtained by Griffith and Kent⁴. It is evident that

TABLE 2—OPTIMISED AND EXPERIMENTAL STRUCTURAL PARAMETERS FOR DEWAR BENZENE

Coordinate ^a	Calculated		Experimental	
	MNDO	6-31G ^{*b}	GED ^c	Microwave ^d
R (C ₃ -C ₆)	1.609	1.555	1.574	1.62
R (C ₂ -C ₃)	1.526	1.524	1.523	1.53
R (C ₁ -C ₂)	1.357	1.341	1.345	1.34
R (C ₃ -H ₉)	1.093	1.089	1.134	
R (C ₁ -H ₇)	1.074	1.081	1.124	
β_{165}	117.3	117.5	116.7	
β_{634}	85.3	86.0	85.7	
β_{639}	123.8	121.3	108.0	
β_{328}	129.4	132.3	126.7	
α	117.9	118.0	117.3	

^aBond distance in angstroms; angle in degree.

^b*Ab initio* calculations of Liu *et al.* (Ref. 2).

^cGas-phase electron diffraction results of McNeill and Scholer (Ref. 3).

^dMicrowave results of Griffith and Kent (Ref. 4).

Fig. 2. Structure of Dewar benzene

the structural parameters (Table 2) optimised by the MNDO method are comparable to both the *ab initio* theoretical results and the experimental values. In the case of dipole moment, the MNDO method predicts a value of 0.0858 D while the *ab initio* value is 0.0857 D. The experimental value of the dipole moment is 0.0437 D.

The structures 12, 15 and 18 have large heats of formation. The presence of a bicyclo[1.1.0]butane moiety in them may account for this. This is in agreement with the calculated energy for the bicyclo[1.1.0]butane isomer among the C₄H₆ systems, already re-

ported in the literature⁵. Potgieter⁶ reported the synthesis of three bicyclopropenyl molecules. This author reports that Dewar benzene has only transitory existence lasting through hours. Since the ΔH_f value for benzvalene, evaluated in our study, is comparable with those for Dewar benzene and prismane, benzvalene and other intermediate compounds (8, 9, 11–16) should also be formed, with similar transitory lives. Though Potgieter reported the formation of bicyclopropenyl molecules, he did not indicate anything about their lifetimes. The values of ΔH_f for these compounds evaluated in our study may be taken to indicate that they can also exist only for a brief period.

Greenberg and Liebman⁷, based on their *ab initio* study of (CH)₆ isomers evaluated the heats of formation of five isomers (Table 3). Here, the ΔH_f values are quoted with reference to that for benzene (from each absolute value of ΔH_f that of benzene is subtracted). The authors concluded, based on these data, that 3,3'-bicyclopropenyl is the least stable of these isomers. The authors reported that the STO-4-31G calculation gives the correct ordering of isomer stabilities but the values obtained by the STO-3G method are closer to the experimental heats of formation. How-

ever, in the latter, the positions of Dewar benzene and prismane are interchanged. The present MNDO method reproduces the correct order of isomer stabilities and also has ΔH_f values closer to the experimental ones. We have extended this method to a few more strained C₆H₆ isomers in this study. These strained isomers (24–30, Table 3) have higher heats of formation compared to the isomers reported by Greenberg and Liebman. The higher values are justifiable because each of the structures 24 to 30 has enhanced molecular strain. In structure 24, a bicyclobutane moiety is coupled with a cyclopropene moiety, both of which are strained molecules even individually⁵. Structure 25 is a variant of Dewar benzene in which a double bond has been shifted to the central position. This is expected to induce strain at the two carbon atoms (central ones) resulting in lengthening of the C–C single bond parallel to the double bond. In structure 26, there is a tetrahedrane moiety, which is a high energy isomer of C₄H₄. Therefore, this structure is likely to have considerable strain and therefore has less stability compared to either structure 24 or 25. Structure 27 is a tricyclo[1.1.1.0^{1,3}]pentane (or propellane) type species⁸. Here, the central bond is turned inward, having all the four sp³ hybridised bonds on one side of a plane, introducing high strain to the structure. This is reflected in a higher ΔH_f value for the molecule.

The other three isomers, i.e. 28, 29 and 30, have relative ΔH_f values ranging from 150 to 179 kcal mol⁻¹ indicating increasing structural strain in them. Structures 28, 29 and 30 have a cyclopropene moiety in common and the carbon atoms carrying the double bond form a part of a four-membered ring. The cyclopropene moiety found in 3,3'-bicyclopropenyl molecule (23) introduces a lot of strain. This could be seen from the MNDO and *ab initio* calculations (Table 3), where 3,3'-bicyclopropenyl has the largest heat of formation among the isomers of (CH)₆. These strained compounds have high olefin strain energy (OSE)⁹. [The OSE is the difference in energy between the olefin (generally strained) and the corresponding hydrogenated species]. In structure 28, the C₂–C₃ single bond length is stretched to 1.58 Å (compared to the normal C–C distance of 1.53 Å) due to the strain at the double

TABLE 3—RELATIVE HEATS OF FORMATION FOR SOME C₆H₆ ISOMERS

Structure no.	$\Delta H_f / \text{kcal mol}^{-1}$		
	STO-3G ^a	STO 4-31G ^a	MNDO
1	0.0	0.0	0.0
7	78.7	102.2	68.5
10	68.2	104.5	80.4
17	92.5	149.5	100.7
23	142.9	154.4	119.8
24			123.4
25			124.4
26			126.8
27			151.0
28			151.5
29			176.3
30			179.1

^a*Ab initio* calculations of Greenberg and Liebman (Ref. 7).

bond. This stretching partly relieves the strain by increasing the bond angle at the sp^2 hybridised carbons (C_1 and C_4). In structure **29**, this type of single bond stretching increases to 1.62 Å, but this bond is a part of a cyclopropane ring, which introduces further strain, leading to higher ΔH_f . But in structure **30**, such a stretching is made more difficult as a double bond replaces a single bond, which further increases the strain on the molecule. These arguments are substantiated by the trends in relative ΔH_f values for these three systems.

The ΔH_f values evaluated by the MNDO method adopted in the present study agree satisfactorily with those obtained by the *ab initio* method of Greenberg and Liebman⁷. These values are also close to those obtained experimentally. These substantiate the validity of the MNDO method applied to the study of C_6H_6 isomers. Also, the *ab initio* calculation of Liu *et al.*² and the experimental data of McNeill and Scholer³ and Griffith and Kent⁴ for the isomer Dewar benzene are comparable to the MNDO results. The results obtained in the present study indicate that the MNDO method is a useful and reliable approximation for both

structural optimisation and evaluation of the ΔH_f values.

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